

PERCEPTIONS

UNDERSTAND THE IMPACT OF NOVEL TECHNOLOGIES, SOCIAL MEDIA, AND PERCEPTIONS IN COUNTRIES ABROAD ON MIGRATION FLOWS AND THE SECURITY OF THE EU & PROVIDE VALIDATED COUNTER APPROACHES, TOOLS AND PRACTICES

D2.4 Collection of threats and security issues

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Executive Summary

This report analyses the issues, problems or threats (real or perceived) regarding current movements and processes of migration. A database/matrix has been set up based on the reports provided by partners of PERCEPTIONS project. The analysis of that database composed of 138 documents shows a list of 177 threats, real or perceived by the authors of the reports.

The list of existing threats and border security issues is based on prior research and reports of security practitioners, policymakers and civil society organisation. It presents a structured collection of such main threats/issues based on these secondary data. Based on the in-depth examination of these 138 entries, the analysis provided a database that analyses the documents and threats and classified them according to different items.

The importance of this report lies in analysing which threats are identified in prior research and reports by security practitioners, policymakers and civil society organisation. Those threats and risks affect different referent objects and could be related to a mismatch between expectations about and 'reality' in Europe. The reports represent mainly the perspective of host/destination countries as long as those documents are more abundant in the database. If the information is analysed with respect to the referent object, threats related to host countries amounted for nearly half of the total percentage.

This means that the conclusions we have reached are, in part, broadly the vision of the destination countries. This conclusion points to the need of the PERCEPTIONS project to assess the perspectives and narratives of countries which migrants transit through as well as of their countries of origin. In this sense, this report is also the view of the institutional actors (think tanks, policymakers, NGOs and security practitioners) that needs and will be complemented with the perspective of migrants, their perceptions and narratives, and other practitioners from different sectors, in PERCEPTIONS project.

Documents from academic organisations and think tanks are predominant in the database followed by others, such as media, newspapers, and governmental and policymaking bodies. The nature of these documents, in term of the level of the organisation that wrote or publish them, is mainly national. Hence, international and comparative research as PERCEPTIONS project will be welcome. Moreover, most of the documents date from 2018 and 2019 while they portray threats related to 2015 and 2016, thus updated research is also needed.

The qualitative analysis, and its comparison with the literature reviewed at the beginning of this deliverable and in deliverable 2.2 of PERCEPTIONS project, show that no special new phrasing of threats is done. The qualitative research shows how each group of people perceive each other's role in the problem and issues and also the facts and event considered as threatening. Sometimes narratives about different threats are linked to others.

Concerning threats identified through the reports, an important finding is that the threat of violent radicalisation and terrorism seems prominent in most of the reports of host countries; this means an imaginary that links this threat with those who come from outside. Notably, host countries appeared more worried about the consequences that might come with the arrival of migrants than the threats migrants may suffer in their journeys to arrive in Europe. Some of the "expected" threats, based on the academic review carried out in the first part of this research, barely appear in the documents collected, such as corruption and modern slavery.

Another remarkable finding is the salience of border security. The documents consider issues at borders, such as detention and deportation or human smuggling and trafficking, control over their

borders and disputes in the presence of large flows of immigrants. Borders are mentioned as deserving special attention regarding the possible entry of criminals/terrorists who can cross under the chaos of such large numbers of people.

Among the actors who identify the threats, the ones who have included the broadest view of aspects or issues related to security are academic and think-tanks reports, while documents by security practitioners are much narrower in focus. Civil society reports analyse issues such as human trafficking and emphasise that the children and women are particularly vulnerable migration groups.

An additional analysis on the impact of new technologies on migration, perceptions and threats is included in this report. However, there are very few reports that are focused on and mainly related to technologies and its relationship with migration along with diverse threats. New technologies are today, a very powerful weapon for organized crimes and illegal trafficking of immigrants. This means that Europe needs to create new methods to prevent and fight the challenges that arise from these threats concerning ICTs. PERCEPTIONS project is a great opportunity to observe and analyse the importance of these and their impact on these issues.

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Acronyms & Abbreviations

Term	Description
SLR	Systematic Literature Review
WP	Work Package
OCG	Organised Crime Group
P2P	Peer-to-peer
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation

1 Introduction

This deliverable presents a list of existing threats and border security issues based on prior research and security practitioners, policymakers and civil society organisation reports. It presents a structured collection of such main threats/issues based on secondary data and existing research specifically reports by those types of organisations, i.e. it summarises what studies and stakeholders consider the most important aspects of security.

The final matrix of documents¹ is composed of 138 reports that provide information about 177 threats and issues linked to migration movements of people across borders. These documents have been collected from both EU and non-EU collaborating partners. Based on the in-depth examination of these 138 reports, the analysis provided a database to organise the information and to develop a series of threats classified according to different themes.

The importance of this report lies in analysing which threats are identified in prior research and reports by security practitioners, policymakers and civil society organisation. Those threats and risks affect different referent objects and could be related to a mismatch between expectations about and ‘reality’ in Europe. While perceptions of Europeans towards migration and immigrants have been studied in abundance, the literature on migrants’ perceptions towards Europe and Europeans is scander.

In this deliverable, the following structure has been followed. In section 2, a far-reaching analysis of the relevant academic literature is completed in order to clarify the concept of threats/risks/problems, the idea of “hard-soft” threats and the identification of “security-non-security” issues. It will provide a list of benchmarks for security with the aim of knowing what different actors consider the most important aspects of security.

Section 3 describes the methodology used in this deliverable, collection of data and analysis. A combined qualitative and quantitative analysis of the information has been done based on the template filled with the information identified in the reports. The fourth section contains the analysis dedicated to the matrix/database, a classification of the reports compiled has been made by countries that sent the reports, types of authors/organisations who wrote the reports, and year of publication.

The fifth section comprises the qualitative analysis of the threats and issues stated in the reports. Based on the previous review of the literature and classifications (section 2), the information provided by the 169 documents collected and studied is analysed to point out the wording related to threats.

Section 6 describes the list of threats of the database and carries out a quantitative descriptive analysis. It includes different classifications according to different variables assessed in the templates, and a series of figures and tables are presented to support the analysis. The information received about the threats is analysed by referent objects, areas of security policy, type of country (origin, transit, and destiny)², year/s in which the issue is identified and also by the actors who identified the threat: policymakers, civil society organisation, security practitioners, academic/think tanks and others. New

¹ The criteria for inclusion/exclusion criteria of documents is explained in the section of Methodology.

² The classification according to country type is based on the study by Forin and Healy (2018), in which countries are classified as: origin, transit and destination.

issues, not perfectly related to the threats identified in the literature, are also analysed in the final part of this section (section 6.9).

Section 7 is dedicated to the small number of documents that indicate that technology influences threats. The importance of technology understood in a broad sense (Internet, social networks, instant messaging applications, etc.) is stated in 8 documents of the total collected. They pay special attention to the influence of technology on the expansion of violent radicalisation and terrorism.

Finally, the main conclusions reached after the analysis of the total number of documents are presented in section 8. Overall, it can be established that the documents represent mainly destination and arrival countries and that this group of countries seems mainly focused on the prevention of violent radicalization and terrorism. This suggests that Europe is more concerned with alleviating the threats that could derive from migration than with the threats suffered by migrants themselves.

This identifies a major limitation in the discussion of migration to Europe, namely the over-representation of threats and security issues in destination countries, while largely being silent on threats and security issues in countries of origin and transit. Thus, we can say that the database foregrounds a skewed vision of threats. This makes PERCEPTIONS a great opportunity to carry out fieldwork in those countries with respect to threat and security narratives and perceptions of migrants.

2 Literature review

2.1 The migration and security nexus revisited

Sarah Collinson assured in 2000 that “much of the anxiety linked with migration may be considered unfounded or, at least, disproportional to the actual or direct ‘threats’ that it poses” (Collinson, 2000, p. 302). The process of linking societal issues to security, called *securitization*, has been tracked back in the literature to the beginning of the 90s with the work of the Copenhagen School with Ole Waever’s and Barry Buzan’s notion of *human security*.

At that time, Huysmans was one of the first authors to advise about the risk of analysing migration as a security problem, the reason was that it “will contribute to the (re)production of the security drama” (Huysmans, 1995, p. 69). Since then, many authors have pointed to the unintended and/or negative secondary effects of the discourse linking migration and security issues within the European Union (e.g. Guild, 2003). Emphasizing restrictions and controls in itself implies a negative portrayal of groups of migrants and that discourse can lead to xenophobic or discriminatory ideas or practices among an ‘ignorant’ or ‘easily persuaded’ public (Collinson, 2000, p. 302; Huysmans, 2000). At the same time, securitisation makes the inclusion of immigrants in European societies more difficult while further diminishing the chances of promoting multicultural policies (Huysmans, 2000, p. 753; Papademetriou, 2003). Some radical parties may take political advantage of the discourses on the securitisation of migration. Thus, in general terms, this approach to migration has a negative effect on immigrants and the receiving societies as a whole.

Among the more determined critics over securitising discourse, Huysmans has highlighted the dangers of securitizing societal issues such as migration (Huysmans, 1995; 2000; 2006). In this vein, Geddes draws on Waever’s ideas on framing migration as a security issue, arguing that:

...security discourse is characterised by dramatizing an issue as having absolute priority... ‘Security’ is thus a self-referential practice, not a question of measuring seriousness of various threats and deciding when they ‘really’ are dangerous to some object... It is self-referential because it is in this practice that the issue becomes a security issue (Waever in Geddes, 2000, p. 26).

This discourse seems to produce a ‘self-fulfilling’ prophecy: “once turned into a security problem, the migrant appears as the other who has entered (or who desires to enter) a harmonious world and just by having entered it, has disturbed the harmony” (Huysmans, 1995, p. 59). This author rejects the concept of ‘societal security’ to distinguish the referent object from those of ‘hard’ threats and also criticizes attempts to balance the securitisation discourse with a discourse that highlights the benefit and profits that migrants bring to receiving societies.

However, this discourse exists, and as a consequence deserve cautious attention. Immigration is properly typified within that paradigm of security or not, i.e. is framing immigration as a security issue necessary? As Collyer notes, the question lies in whether potential dangers of migration should be explored within a security framework or viewed as simply ‘problems’ to be addressed (Collyer, 2006, p. 256). It is also important to identify the framing of immigration as a security issue is trying to achieve. In line with Austin’s seminal work on ‘speech acts’ or ‘illocutionary acts’, Waever et al. point out that presenting a public issue as a serious security threat means elevating this issue to an absolute priority.

Moreover, the logical consequence will be to take emergency measures or an exceptional course of action (Waever et al., 1993; Buzan et al., 1998).

2.2 Threats related to migration. The perspective of host countries

Some essential questions have to be answered in order to classify a phenomenon a security risk. First of all, the threat has to be thoroughly defined and characterised. Secondly, the referent object of security, i.e. that which is in danger or is being threatened and thus in need of protection, must also be clearly identified. And thirdly, the logic that links the threat and the referent object must be plainly stated so that the chain linking the causes (threat) and consequences (to referent objects) is traceable. In one way or another, all those concepts need to be at least tacitly expressed within an analysis of migration discourses. In terms of discourse, the framing of an issue as a security matter occurs when a discourse takes the form of presenting something as an existential threat (Buzan et al., 1998).

Despite the fact that some scholars linked immigration and security long ago (Miller, 1998, p. 18) or even perceived security rationales as the backdrop for most countries' restrictive immigration legislation, it was not until the 1990s that the migration-security pairing was more widely addressed. Myron Weiner (1993; 1995) led the way in the study of the immigration phenomenon from a security/stability framework, paying particular attention to immigrants' involvement in political violence.³ He analysed some associated 'threats' with immigrants and/or refugees: (1) are armed and become involved in activities related to the traffic of weapons or drugs, (2) ally with opposition and oppose the receiving country's regime and (3) when refugees and migrants oppose the regime of their home country (Weiner 1993; 1995). Thus, the foreign population is understood as a risk to internal stability and security, as well as an international security threat (among states).⁴

After that classification, some others have been developed. Tsardinidis and Guerra (2000) identified some "threats from the South": the question of political stability (including the threat of terrorist attacks), proliferation of weapons, regional conflicts and the worsening of economic and social conditions within countries in Africa. All these factors can increase international migration and impact in a real or perceived way into European countries' national identity, economic well-being and public order. Political stability can also be threatened by immigration and xenophobia and migrant trafficking is seen as affecting national sovereignty (Tsardinidis and Guerra, 2000). Another typical example of such threats linked to migrants relates to their involvement in activities perceived as social burdens due to their implications for crime and delinquency. In this case, these illegal activities are thought to worsen crime rates or delinquency records.

Lucassen in 2005 identified three categories of perceived threats to receiving countries: cultural, socio-economic and political (cited in Castles, de Haas and Miller, 2009). This classification stems from several analyses around the change of the millennium that identified a new climate of uncertainty and insecurity in Western Europe and "a correspondingly broadened security agenda" (Collinson, 2000, p.

³ Some other scholars from international relations also began to analyse the security dimensions of migration and refugees in the context of globalisation, for example Miler (1997; 1998), Jessen-Petersen (1994) and Zimmermann (1995).

⁴ In the field of security studies, the 1990s provided an opportunity for redefining security in a post-Cold War context. Redefining security gave rise to a debate on the incorporation of new threats, not only of military nature but also 'soft' threats, new referent objects and new rationales for linking new threats and referent objects. The Copenhagen school specially contributed to broadening the understanding of referent objects with new concepts such as 'societal security' (Buzan 1991, 1993; Buzan et. al 1998; Waever et al. 1993).

302) that incorporated a wide range of the so-called 'soft' security issues. In this sense, for some authors, the link comes from the changes in the concept of security, which has been used with a wider meaning to include a great range of challenges, risks and tensions "at different levels and of different orders, many of which are more perceived than real" (Collinson, 2000, p. 303).

Three main referent objects related to the stability and governance in receiving states were specified in the academic research, particularly in two domains: economy, identity and cultural practices. In the economic domain, the analyses of the impact of immigration referred to essentially two aspects: on the one hand, the labour market and the competition for scarce resources (Borjas, 1996; Ullman, 1995; Alvarado and Creedy, 1998; Money, 1999) and on the other hand, the sustainability of welfare states in developed countries (Freeman, 1986; Stalker, 1994; Razin and Sadka, 1995; and some years later Baldwin-Edwards, 2002). A second realm is that of identity and cultural practices. Globalisation debates in the area of international relations emphasise the transnational and trans-border character of movements of people that are analysed by their effects in cultural terms. In that sense, Weiner points out that "migrants can be perceived as a threat to the major societal values of the receiving country" (Weiner, 1993, p. 103). New characteristics of migrants and refugees seem to challenge identities of citizens settled in receiving societies, and as a consequence, their new values and cultural practices are perceived as a risk or cultural threat to social cohesion and shared security (Schieffer, 1997, p. 97; and years later Sartori, 2001).

PERCEPTIONS project has updated the literature on this topic in deliverable 2.2. Thus, PERCEPTIONS' SLR has identified the key threats to host countries, migrants and both. One of them is "violent radicalisation and terrorism" that is described as "host states and citizens [which] widely perceive a positive correlation between increased migration and increased terrorism." (Deliverable 2.2, p. 70). Migration is linked to terrorism in two ways. Some authors have portrayed the September 11 attacks as increasing the connection of previously separate agendas of integration and migration control in Europe (Carrera 2006; Joppke 2007: 8). Debates on accommodation may have been deepened and speeded up by the information on Madrid and London bombings. The conclusions of the investigations on the Madrid and London bombings in 2004 and 2005 which found that the attacks were perpetrated by long-term resident immigrants highlighted a failure in integration policies in these countries; youth radicalised into violence. Those results led to policy convergence on the need for better integration across European countries and led to new steps and measures in the EU. An example is the European Council's agreement in November 2004 on 'common basic principles' of immigrant integration policy (Joppke 2007). The second way to link migration and terrorism is done in border crossing policies, i.e., that migration flows provide conduits for the spread of international terrorism (Bermejo, 2009, p. 219).

Four others aspects stated in the recent academic literature, since 2015 (Deliverable 2.2) have been mentioned in previous academic literature, as stated above, at different moments: (1) 'minor, serious and organised crime' which includes the increase of crime rates due to different reasons, (2) 'disease' understood as migrants carrying infectious diseases, (3) civil unrest or political stability and (4) the economy.

2.3 Threats to migrants and to migrants and host countries

2.3.1 Critiques to host countries vision. A wider look to include migrants as referent objects

The initial classifications of risks and referent objects have posed some problems (Bermejo, 2005, p. 271) that today are still present. Most of the analyses lacked a precise definition of threat and there

was no clear explanation of the link between threats and referent objects, i.e. how those threats were to affect particular referent objects in danger is frequently not stated. The identification of risks and referent objects lacked a clear and precise definition of the threat due to the use of vague and broad concepts (immigrants or/and refugees or demographic threats). Besides, not all of the activities identified as threatening considered the same number of immigrants. For example, there is no distinction made between the risks posed by a large number of immigrants versus the risks posed by small but well settled and organised groups. This broad identification may lead to problems of criminalising or securitising large groups of people. And in order to avoid that inexactness, the focus should be the activities and not the groups of populations. In addition, Brochmann points out a tendency in most receiving countries to focus on flows of people rather than individuals. The perception of immigrants as representing flows rather than individual human beings “reinforces the threat images of immigration, and has contributed to a tendency of *politicization* of immigration” with the utilisation of metaphors like ‘flood’, ‘invasion’, ‘hungry hordes’ that play on people’s fears and insecurity (Brochmann, 1999, p. 331).

A second group of critiques comes from the characterisation of receiving societies (referent objects). Not only are receiving societies not homogeneous but when immigrants are perceived as a cultural or social cohesion problem the cultural values of both immigrants and receiving populations come into conflict. Thus, the degree and scope of problems will depend on factors such as the distance and difference between cultures and practices (Miller, 1998, p. 19). Furthermore, the perception of immigrants as economic or welfare burdens depends on the receiving society’s economic situation. In a prosperous and growing economic time, the ‘same immigrants’ who are seen as welfare burdens can be perceived, instead, as necessary for the maintenance of economic growth.

This research in the context of PERCEPTIONS has taken two decisions in order to overcome, at least partially those critiques. The first is to include the threats that migration processes pose to migrants on the one hand, and to migrants and host countries together, on the other. Among the more prominent threats that migrants experience during the journeys, the academic literature reviewed for deliverable 2.2 singled out death, detention and deportation, discrimination, violence, abuse and modern slavery. It further suggested that journeys have become more difficult and harder, incentives for the use of illegal and dangerous paths and the contact to smugglers and traffickers that immigrants are aware of the risks and assume that death in the process is a real option. Detention and deportation are also seen as a threat related to migration among migrants. Discrimination once in the country of destiny is also perceived as a threat. Migrants fear suffering racism, sexual harassment, poverty or discrimination in employment or education due to their race, ethnicity, religion or class. Violence and abuse appear also in the academic literature as threats perceived and suffered by migrants during their journeys to Europe and also once in the receiving countries. Finally, modern slavery due to long periods of stay in transit countries or the lack of legal status was mentioned as a threat to migrants.

Four types of threats were identified as affecting both migrants and receiving countries: human smuggling and trafficking, corruption, domestic violent extremism and environmental problems. All of them are perceived as a threat to life and wellbeing. The panorama of all the threats (real or perceived as such by different actors) and related to migration processes, as they are classified in D2.2, is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. List of threats

Object / subject	Threats
Migrants	Death

	Detention and Deportation
	Discrimination
	Violence and Abuse
	Modern Slavery
Host countries	Violent Radicalisation and Terrorism
	Minor, Serious and Organised Crime
	Economic
	Civil Unrest
	Disease
Migrants and host countries	Human Smuggling and Trafficking
	Corruption
	Domestic Violent Extremism
	Environmental

2.3.2 Migrants/migration and security-related policy areas

A second decision has been to pay detailed attention to those threats that are related to security-policy areas as identified in PERCEPTIONS D.2.3 (table 2). It means that in order to assess, tackle and respond to those issues, security forces play a key role although they can work in coordination with other actors. The first area is violent radicalisation and terrorism. Despite the increase of terrorism during the last two decades (Crone and Harrow, 2011), immigrants (in general) and second-generation migrants or citizens of immigrant background are the focus for radicalisation and recruitment of this religious wave of terrorism. A second area of public policies is border management/control. The processes of migration necessarily involve the crossing of at least the border of the country of arrival. Most of the times, it involves the crossing of several borders in which police forces are in charge of identification, control of documents and security in general. Among the threats identified earlier, this fact will serve as guidance in the analysis of the documents compiled. We will also consider two other areas related to security-related policy: minor, serious and organised crime and human smuggling and trafficking. As stated above, criminality and its increase due to migration movements are one of the long-standing issues identified in the academic literature. On the other side, human smuggling and trafficking have become a growing problem and worry of migrants and host countries in recent decades.

Table 2. Security related-policy areas

Security-related areas
Violent radicalisation and terrorism
Minor, serious and organised crime
Human smuggling and trafficking
Border security

3 Methodology

This section outlines the methodology used to collect, select and analyse the data on which the results of this deliverable are based.

3.1 Methodological approach

The approach chosen for the collection of threats and security issues in D2.4 is twofold. On the one hand, a quantitative approach aimed to identify the number of documents and reports on threats and border issues in relation to migration movements published by security practitioners, policymakers and civil society organisations since 2015 across partner countries was collected. These materials create a matrix as input for WP5. On the other hand, a qualitative approach was chosen in order to understand the concept of threat/risks/issues, level of potential danger related to it, the group or countries affected, etc., which will be reported in this document.

3.2 Template to systematise the information, instructions and clarifications

The template given to partners for data collection is included in Annex I and comprises the variables used to identify the documents/reports and the threats included in those documents. We incorporated a very brief set of instructions:

“General Instructions

T2.4. aims to identify main issues that affect security/border security caused by narratives, rumours or false images or mismatch between a narrative/expectation and the reality and included in reports from security practitioners, policymakers and civil society organisations.

The publication of these reports should be from 2015 onwards.”

The idea of these very scant instructions was to avoid predisposition and allow spontaneous answers according to partner’s ideas about the relationship between threat and migration, i.e. we wanted respondent partners to work with their own ideas of threats after the initial discussions and debates in the PERCEPTIONS project. Nevertheless, some clarifications needed to be made when asked by partners:

Firstly, some clarifications were made to partners:

“In the task description, only border-related threats are mentioned. In your own data collection, please use a broader view of threats to make sure we don’t miss out important information. This means also including threats to migrants and threats by migrants (e.g. fears about radicalisation), as they are often part of migration narratives about the EU”

“Some examples we came across during our literature analysis so far as well as more general issues. We decided to use a broad definition of threats, including border issues as well as what we – for ease of phrasing – called “threats to migrants” and “threats by migrants”. Examples of various security issues/threats that come to mind are:

- **Security issues/threats by migrants:** fears about terrorism, fears for labour market/own jobs, fears about ‘dilution of own culture’,

- **Security issues/threats to migrants:** wrong perceptions about the educational status of migrants as ‘largely uneducated’ threaten possibilities for integration, legal systems especially around borders that are applied too strictly or in a vindictive way, negative perceptions that lead to intolerance/violence, negative perceptions can lead to immense pressures to migrants totally ‘renounce’ home culture/language/customs, negative perceptions can lead to isolation in the host country, ‘hostile environment’ policies that aim at deterring migration can cause hardships during transit/arrival
- **Border issues:** migrants report that they make very strategic choices about which countries they travel to first depending on legal/visa requirements, often high mobility of migrants moving between countries, issues of ‘symbolic bordering’ – i.e. the way host communities talk about migrants creates psychological borders that can threaten integration” (Bayerl, email 13th Nov 19; 28th Nov. 19)”.

3.3 Data collection and inclusion criteria and database limitations

The fieldwork, collection of documents, began in 9th October 2019 and ended 9th February 2020. To carry out this task the following partners have participated and collected and sent us information about their countries, other countries or about the European Union in general:

- Koinonia Caritas Cyprus (CARITAS), Cyprus.
- Alma Mater Studiorum Universita di Bologna (UNIBO), Italy
- Euro-Arab Foundation for Higher Studies (FUNDEA), provided information about Tunisia
- Centre de Recherche en Economie Appliquée pour le Developpement (CREAD), Algeria
- SINUS Markt- und Sozialforschung GmbH (SINUS), Germany
- Sheffield Hallam University (CENTRIC), UK
- University of Antwerp (UANTWERPEN), Belgium
- Center for the Study of Democracy (CSD), Bulgaria
- Kosovar Centre for Security Studies (KCSS), Kosovo
- Kentro Meleton Asfaleias - Center for Security Studies (KEMEA), Greece
- Hellenic Police (HP), Greece
- Egyptian Center for Innovation and Technology Development (ECITD), Egypt
- International Centre for Migration Policy Development (ICMPD), Austria
- University Rey Juan Carlos (URJC), Spain

The different types of organisations/partners that provide data allow us to reduce the possible bias in the selection of reports based on their own preferences. Nevertheless, we cannot deny the possibility of any bias in the selection decisions.

Firstly, the information provided by partners was compiled and organised. An example of the tables sent to each of the providers is presented in Annex II. They were sent in order to confirm the panorama of threats that stemmed from the documents sent by each of them. The information was confirmed or discussed individually.

Secondly, once confirmed it was organised and cleared. Initially, the total number of entries in the database was 171, covering a total of 155 documents related to 199 threats. After clearing all the information, duplicate documents, published before 2015, those texts that didn’t cover migration or do not talk about threats, the total number of entries is 138 documents covering 177 threats.

One of the problems we have had to face has been the idiomatic difficulty of some reports that only exist in the language of the country it comes from which we do not speak (e.g. Arabic or Dutch). Some of these reports were provided with a summary in English, but others were not. We were able to translate some of them: those in Italian, Dutch and German when needed. In case the description was not enough in order to identify the document or the threat and no possibility of translation was available, documents had been excluded from analysis, although not without first requesting information to the respective partners.

As part of the partner data, we received a number of articles from digital newspapers. These provide valuable background information about the countries, but could not be taken into account since they are not official documents and may have biases depending on the sources, they come from⁵. We have also excluded documents/reports that were provided by more than two partners in order to avoid duplications.

⁵ We only included a small part of them, those from the countries with no national reports.

4 The dataset

The final dataset is composed of 138 documents and incorporates the variables describing the documents themselves (meta-data; see template) as well as the variables related to the threats perceived. Only documents that include or mention one of the possible threat types in the classification were reviewed. We do not know what percentage, of the total number of documents produced by these organisations in these countries, this is equivalent to; that is to say, whether the majority of documents produced by these institutions contain mentions of these security issues or not. In consequence, we cannot know whether the reports that mention threats are a small part of the total reports published by those institutions or a large part of their production.

In the following, we present the analysis of the documents along with a number of variables: the country that sent the report, the type of actor/institution that published the report, the type of threat identified, the governmental level of the organisation who published the report and the year of publication of the documents.

4.1 Classification and analysis of the documents by partner countries that sent the reports

First, a classification of the documents according to the country of our partners (i.e., the country in which they are based) was done. This information is elaborated in figure 1⁶. As figure 1 shows, partner(s) from Germany (23.9%), Greece (17.4%) and UK (14.5%) provided the larger number of reports when asked to provide reports from security practitioners, policymakers and civil society organisations dealing with “issues that affect security/border security caused by narratives, rumours or false images or mismatch between a narrative/expectation and the reality”. It is interesting that there are fewer from/about Italy (5.8%) and particularly Spain (4.3%), given that they are the main entry points into Europe for migration. The lower number of documents from these countries may be due to different reasons. These include the absence of work linking migratory movements to such issues, the smaller number of such organizations or a deliberate intention to avoid linking migration with threats or security issues.

Figure 1. Frequencies of documents by partner countries

⁶ The category "Europe" has been used as a residual category for those documents that did not mention the specific country, but referred to Europe as a whole.

4.2 Classification and analysis of the documents by type of country (origin, transit and destination)

A further classification of the documents has been made according to the type of country the information stems from. Based on Forin, Roberto & Healy, Claire (2018), countries in the sample were classified into three categories: origin, transit and destination. Countries of origin are those outside Europe from which migrants leave for the continent, although on their routes they may be countries of transit from other countries outside Europe. Countries of transit include countries such as Bulgaria, Serbia and the former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia, because they are "largely seen by migrants and authorities alike as 'transit countries' to be crossed in order to reach Northern and Western Europe" (Forin and Healy, 2018, p. 54). Destination countries are the rest of the countries located within the European soil. For our sample of countries:

- Origin: Algeria, Tunisia and Egypt.
- Transit: Kosovo and Bulgaria.
- Destination: Italy, Spain, Germany, UK, Greece, Cyprus, Austria and Belgium.⁷

Analysing the documents received and classifying them according to the type of country to which the partner belongs (countries that are covered by the documents sent), the results are as follows on a total of 138 documents included:

Table 3. Percentage of documents by type of country

Type of country	Frequencies of documents	Percentage of documents
Origin	18	13%
Transit	10	7.2%
Destination	110	79.8%
TOTAL	138	100%

According to table 3, it is important to highlight that, due to the fact that we received more information from destination countries because they are represented in greater numbers in PERCEPTIONS consortium than origin and transit countries, the information was more abundant about destination countries. It should be added that the percentage of documents received from destination countries (79.8% of the total) is mostly due to the fact that out of the total of thirteen countries contributing to this database, eight are classified as destination countries.

Therefore, the information we include from these countries is greater than for origin and transit countries as there are only two transit and three origin countries in our sample of countries. This produces an overrepresentation of destination countries, and their perception of security issues, that will affect results at different points of the analysis.

⁷ This classification is not absolute. We need to emphasize that despite the fact that some of these countries can be several categories at the same time; some countries may be transit or destination depending on the circumstances or can be both (depending on the migrants). They can be countries of destination and transit at the same time for different groups of immigrants but also they can change their role over the years. We take this classification from PERCEPTIONS proposal. Austria is not considered in this classification as far as the dedicated partner sent us many reports referring to Europe more generally, not to the country.

4.3 Classification and analysis of the documents by type of actor who identifies the threat

Our dataset contains information collected by the partners of PERCEPTIONS project. The information asked and included in the database is mainly “grey literature” produced by civil society organisations, governmental institutions, policymakers and security practitioners, but it also academic literature/ think-tanks, mainly think tanks reports and other sources. We classified the organisations following the work done in PERCEPTIONS Deliverable 2.1. An example of the sources included in the categories are the following:

- **“Civil society/NGOs”** comprises international organisations such as The Global Community Engagement and Resilience Fund (GCERF) or Human Right Watch and International Amnesty; networks of organisations such the Platform for International Cooperation on Undocumented Migrants or Doctors without Borders, and smaller/national ones such as Migration Coalition (cooperation between various Flemish CSOs) in Belgium.
- Among the category **“Governmental/ Policymaking Body”**, reports from the EU Agency for Fundamental Rights are included or national reports from different governmental organisations such as the Federal Office for Migration and Refugees from Germany, the State Agency for National Security in Bulgaria or documents from National Councils of Ministers are included.
- Reports from institutions such as EUROPOL, FRONTEX, and EU Agency for Fundamental Rights are classified in **“Security/LEA/Border Agency”**. Also reports from the Algerian Police or the Federal Criminal Police Office in Germany. In this group, most of these reports stem from European agencies and organisations.

Despite the fact that **“academic and think tank”** reports were not a primary object of this analysis, the relevance of the type reports compiled and the institutions justified their inclusion. Documents from think tanks such as the International Centre for Counter Terrorism (ICCT) –The Hague or the Istituto per gli studi di Politica Internazionale (ISPI) in Italy, or the Migration Policy Institute provided are part of the database.

“Others”: projects such as the Global Detention Project or newspapers and media sources (Sputnik News, BBC, Euroactiv, Africagatenews, Euronews...).

Figure 2. Frequencies of documents by type actor who wrote the report

A classification of the documents according to source type can be found in figure 2. As we can see, the most abundant actors of reports in the database are academic/think-tank (24.6%) followed by others (23.9%) and the governmental and/or policymaking bodies (20.3%). This may indicate, and be due to different reasons: the academic and think-tank sector has researched more about the threats gathered in this research compared to the rest of the actors or because partners preferred to report on academic studies – or because these documents are easier to find. But it certainly gives a certain framing to results.

4.4 Classification and analysis of the documents by level of the organization

Next, we conducted a classification of documents according to the level of the organization that identified or wrote about migration-related threats (figure 3). The classification goes from international to regional/local level.

Figure 3. Frequencies of documents by level of the organization

As figure 3 highlights, documents focusing on the national level are more frequent than the rest (42.8%) followed by those whose author(s) works at the international level (29.7%).

4.5 Classification and analysis of the documents by the year of the document/report

At this point, a classification of the documents will be carried out based on the year of publication of the report. A graph has been drawn up showing the frequency of documents according to the year in which the report is published (figure 4), not according to the year in which the threat identified in the report is located. Classifying the documents based on this variable shows us the longest period of document production, which indicates the year or years in which the different actors who have produced the documents have been most concerned about these threats and false perceptions:

Figure 4. Frequencies of documents by the year of the document

As figure 4 shows, the period with the most publications dealing with migration-related threats is between 2017 and 2019, highlighting 2019 as the year of greatest production (30.4%). It should be noted, however, that we do not know the development in 2020, due mainly to the timing of the request for data collection (up to February 2020). Therefore, it is too early to know whether 2020 will follow the high volume observed in the previous two years. The cutoff date for documents requested and to be included in the database was 2015.

5 Existing threats identified in the database (reports)

As explained above, this deliverable classifies the threats according to different variables, following a number of classifications found in the academic literature on this issue and the previous work done in PERCEPTIONS project. One of these classifications of threats (section 6.1) follows the literature review of the project done in task T2.2 and reported in deliverable D2.2. Here, we present the items (phrasing) included in each of the threats, this means a qualitative analysis of the documents and the description of the threats they mention. In this sense, we found different phrasing of the threats; their description and categorisation are presented below. The wording of the threats in the reports is analysed in relation to the Systematic Literature Review (SLR) done in the project (D2.2) and the section on literature review in this deliverable.

5.1 Phrasing of threats in the reports

5.1.1 Death

The greatest threat to the life of migrants across the literature are hazardous migration journeys. In the reports collected, this threat is also related to travelling illegally across dangerous geographies, mainly the Mediterranean but also to attempts to leave facilities or cross land borders illegally. Deaths occur as refugees and migrants continue to resort to very risky means to cross borders; for example, when migrants cross the Mediterranean Sea to arrive at the European mainland. Sometimes, death is portrayed as avoidable if coordination or rescue operation would function better.

It is further highlighted in the reports that there is a threat for migrants living in the streets or very bad conditions (e.g. without heating, bad alimentation, etc.) or related to gang disputes.

Table 4. Description of Death in the reports

List of threats	Description of the threat in the reports
Death	<p>Number of deaths recorded along land routes at Europe's borders.</p> <p>EU member states' efforts to obstruct rescue efforts by NGOs and relying on Libyan authorities is leading to more deaths of migrants.</p> <p>Transfer of rescue from Italian coast guards to collaboration with Libyan coast guards has contributed to an increase in the deaths of migrants.</p> <p>Potentially fatal incidents during the journey, detention and/or disappearance of unaccompanied children.</p> <p>Border deaths of migrants since the closure of the French border at Ventimiglia.</p> <p>The corpse of a "ten-year-old" child was found in the carriage of an Air France plane that landed at the Parisian airport of Roissy Charles de Gaulle from Abidjan, in Ivory Coast.</p> <p>European Migration Agenda responds to the need to react quickly and decisively to the human tragedy that is lived throughout the basin Mediterranean.</p>

5.1.2 Detention and deportation

Detention and deportation. The academic literature provides with qualitative examples of the fear of migrants to detention and deportation in host countries. Detention and deportation include an imaginary of imprisonment, exploitation, abuse and even death. In the same vein, the reports included

in this dataset, consider detention as a big threat to migrants as they can suffer different kinds of exploitation and abuse. Furthermore, when migrants arrive in a European country they live with a continuous fear of detention, which could be followed by deportation to their country of origin or others. Following the reports, two relevant aspects related to detention and deportation are the reasons and way in which they are done, and the conditions for detention. Conditions of detention centres for migrants are also criticised in some reports that call for the creation of open centres allowing for “decent” living conditions. As the table below shows, detention and deportation also appear related to extremist ideas, violent radicalisation and terrorist organisations.

Table 5. Description of Detention and deportation in the reports

List of threats	Description of the threat in the reports
Detention and deportation	<p>Inadequate shelter conditions; Overcrowded reception/detention centres in Cyprus and Greece; Inadequate staying conditions at reception centres.</p> <p>Several places of detention and official and unofficial camps. Exceeding the maximum time limit of the lawful detention period.</p> <p>Due to overcrowding problems in many reception centres along with Greece, the section reserved for unaccompanied minors are not available, leading this special population to live in general mixed areas.</p> <p>Dire Living Conditions for Asylum Seekers on the Islands, irregular entry at the land border of Greece and Turkey.</p> <p>The dangers and insecurity (unaccompanied) migrant children face in the destination countries (overcrowded reception centres, substandard sanitary conditions...).</p> <p>Security forces rounded up the migrants in and around Algiers.</p> <p>Algeria has rounded up and expelled in masse thousands of Sub-Saharan migrants, including women and children.</p> <p>Detention of migrants in some EU countries.</p> <p>A big number of people get "trapped" between Greece-Albania and Greece- North Macedonia.</p> <p>Greece: Inhumane policies keep children and other vulnerable people trapped in overcrowded camps.</p> <p>Bulgaria has normalised mass detention of migrants and refugees, while it has built a razor-wire fence on its South-Eastern border and regularly undertakes pushbacks at its border with Turkey.</p> <p>Summary detentions, pushbacks and abuses at the border, lack of basic services, a climate of xenophobia and intolerance.</p>

5.1.3 Discrimination

Discrimination is another of the possible threat, common among migrants, analysed in the reports. As we have seen in the SLR done in deliverable 2.2, it is also a complex and nuanced phenomenon that can be both be perceived and experienced in overt and covert forms by migrants. The wording of discrimination in the reports suggests that discrimination often occurs once in destination countries where migrants experience it in the form of racism, xenophobia and prejudices. Prejudices and negative views of refugees and migrants seem to be primarily linked to consider them as “possible” terrorist or radicals, and they are channelled by the mass media and some political parties. The reports

identify a group as particularly in danger of discrimination: unaccompanied minors are a very vulnerable target.

Table 6. Description of Discrimination in the reports

List of threats	Description of the threat in the reports
Discrimination	<p>Migrants believe that the false perceptions that they are security threats lead to them being stopped and searched by law enforcement at will without having done anything wrong.</p> <p>Negative narratives on the scale of the “migrant crisis”; Danish authorities implementing measures to promote Danish values by designating areas with a high proportion of ethnic minority residents as ghettos.</p> <p>UK media was the worse for negative coverage of migration in Europe, with right-wing media being aggressive in their reporting of the migration crisis.</p> <p>Political framing of migration and asylum as a 'threat' influences public opinion in receiving societies.</p> <p>Failure to maintain societal cohesion between the two largest migrant groups in the Netherlands (of Moroccan and Turkish origin) due to perceived incompatibility between welfare state and migration, and the cultural differences of these groups with Dutch values.</p> <p>Difficulties in cultural and educational integration, increase of xenophobia and extreme nationalistic ideology.</p> <p>Immigration as a threat: Explaining the changing pattern of xenophobia in Spain.</p>

5.1.4 Violence and abuse

Violence and abuse include actions such as sexual violence and rape, exploitation and severe psychological distress. As stated in the SLR violence and abuse usually comes with and overlaps with other threats such as detention and deportation and/or discrimination, but also human smuggling and trafficking. Migrants are said to suffer violence from criminal networks or the border officials but also the host citizens. Those abuses and violence can lead to civil unrest.

Table 7. Description of Violence and abuse in the reports

List of threats	Description of the threat in the reports
Violence and abuse	<p>A Cameroonian woman was raped by eight Algerians.</p> <p>Racist intolerance and violent hate crime, over 700 allegations of police violence and theft from migrants.</p> <p>The policy to deal with migrants in transit in Belgium that focuses on dissuasion and detention is considered inefficient and inhumane. It leads to a deterioration of the mental and physical status of migrants and makes them more vulnerable to human smugglers.</p> <p>Kidnapping of illegal immigrants and refugees with the police not even being informed by relatives.</p> <p>Border officials are subjecting people to violence and intimidation in order to prevent them from crossing the borders and deny them access to asylum procedures and international protection.</p> <p>Unlawful treatment and conditions for migrants/asylum seekers.</p>

5.1.5 Violent radicalisation and terrorism

This threat has been included among the threats that affect “host countries” despite the fact that we have to consider that those who have suffered a process of radicalisation and recruitment are also victims of their recruiters. An example is stated in a report that assures that there is a “perception that migrants could be weaponised, smuggled or recruited by terrorist groups”.⁸ Moreover, terrorism and violent radicalisation are considered as a push factor for migration. The more incidents of terrorism and the higher their lethality, the more outward migration from an affected country has been observed.

Academic literature reviewed (deliverable 2.2) shows that “by far the most common threat to host countries associated with migration was violent radicalisation and terrorism.” (Deliverable, 2.2, p.72) Within this collection of reports from academic/think tanks, civil society, governments and policymakers and security/LEAs/border agencies, violent radicalisation and terrorism are the most discussed threats in the reports from countries of destination. The reports conclude that “there are multiple causal relations between (forced/irregular) migration and terrorism – but these are generally perceived as very complex”.⁹ Reports also relate a large number of people/arrivals and overcrowded reception camps with a higher risk¹⁰. In this sense, the arrival of large refugee populations, when not properly handled, is said to increase the risk of attacks in the recipient country by both domestic and transnational terrorists (Schmid, 2016)¹¹.

Table 8. Description of Violent radicalisation and terrorism in the reports

List of threats	Description of the threat in the reports
Violent radicalisation and terrorism	<p>Radicalization threat stemming from migration.</p> <p>The Algerian authorities have expelled 105 Malian migrants accused to be members of a terrorist organisation "Asnar Al din".</p> <p>Terrorism and funding and facilitation of terrorism.</p> <p>Terrorism-related incidents, arrests and trends.</p> <p>Poverty in most parts of the world is contributing to the recruitment of people by extremist groups, trafficking them to the EU and other parts of the world which is a threat to global peace and security.</p> <p>Using the Berlin Christmas market attack in 2016 example, the paper argued that migrants have been involved in Islamic extremist violence.</p> <p>Radicalisation of non-British residents, terrorism and crime.</p> <p>Threats which are linked to, amongst others, the potential return from Syria of so-called foreign terrorist fighters (FTF), Islamic extremism as well as anti-Islam and anti-asylum right-wing extremism.</p> <p>Increased influence of Salafism in Belgium is considered a potential societal problem and breeding ground for jihadism.</p> <p>Radicalisation of Muslim migrant groups in Belgian/Flemish society.</p>

⁸ <https://www.dahrendorf-forum.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/03/Militarising-Migration-Julia-Himrich.pdf>

⁹ https://www.bka.de/SharedDocs/Downloads/DE/Publikationen/JahresberichteUndLagebilder/KriminalitaetImKontextVonZuwanderung/KriminalitaetImKontextVonZuwanderung_2015.html?nn=62336

¹⁰ <https://data2.unhcr.org/en/documents/download/71703>

¹¹ <https://icct.nl/wp-content/uploads/2016/05/Alex-P.-Schmid-Links-between-Terrorism-and-Migration-1.pdf>

	<p>Due to the big number of asylum seekers, the effective tracking, recording and checking are time-consuming processes. As a result, people involved in terrorist acts might also be among the asylum seekers not effectively checked and screened.</p> <p>Given the socio-economic, political, and legal vulnerability of refugees, they are more exposed to experiencing religious radicalization.</p> <p>104 Islamist extremists entered the EU's external borders through irregular migration, between 2014 and 2018, with 28 completing attacks, 37 arrested or killed plotting attacks, and 39 arrested others arrested for illegal involvement with foreign terrorist organisations.</p> <p>The radicalisation of migrants, including refugees, and diaspora members in the context of terrorism; The radicalisation of youth refugees fleeing extremism and war in camps and along migration routes.</p> <p>Infiltration of terrorists among the migration flow, difficulties in cultural and educational integration.</p> <p>In Sicily, two men (an Italian and a Moroccan) were arrested for planning terrorist attacks and making terrorist propaganda.</p> <p>Ten people arrested in Abruzzo for money laundering for terrorist purposes. The funds were also destined for activities attributable to the radical Islamic organization "Al-Nusra", as well as in favour of Imam with residence in Italy.</p> <p>Cases of arrest in two Italian cities in northern and southern Italy (Turin and Foggia) where an Egyptian imam held indoctrination sessions for Muslim children (but mostly born in Italy) with videos of the Isis and an oath to the Caliph.</p> <p>Policy actions against various forms of terrorism which have already been undertaken to spend away from potentially more effective projects towards security.</p> <p>Different threats for the immigrants and Spain: radicalisation, unemployment, etc.</p> <p>A large majority of jihadists in Spain are currently Moroccans or descendants of Moroccans but it is more likely that someone from Morocco will be involved in terrorist activities if they reside in Spain than if they do so in Morocco.</p>
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5.1.6 Minor, serious and organised crime

Minor, serious and organised crime: migrants are widely perceived by host states and citizens as the cause for increasing crime rates (Germany, Spain...). The reason for that relationship takes different forms: they are part (and sometimes victims) of the increasingly profitable “business” of the human trafficking networks, they are related to drug trafficking, prostitution, etc.

Table 9. Description of Minor, serious and organised crime in the reports

List of threats	Description of the threat in the reports
Minor, serious and organised crime	<p>18 African immigrants were involved in the homicide of their comrade, the investigation has revealed that the crime was an account settlement between gang members.</p> <p>Four African immigrants were arrested by the police and jailed for dealing heroin and psychotropics.</p> <p>Weapons trafficking.</p> <p>Organised crime, specifically facilitation of cross-border crime by SOC.</p>

	<p>Assault and crimes against the person.</p> <p>Drug trafficking.</p> <p>Review of cross-border/international crimes and countermeasures.</p> <p>Summary of drug trafficking and other SOC worldwide.</p> <p>Currency counter fighting, cybercrime, drug production/trafficking/distribution, environmental crime, fraud, intellectual property crime, people as a commodity (human trafficking), sports corruption, trafficking of firearms, links between SOC and terrorism.</p> <p>Conservatives want to introduce stronger border controls post-Brexit to make it harder for serious criminals to come to the UK.</p> <p>Locals fear that their society will be significantly affected by the immigrants who will contribute to the increase in criminality rates and terrorist attacks.</p> <p>Irregular arrival, participation in criminality and recidivism, lack of integration and labour market participation, self-harm, limited prospects for returnees in terms of integration, danger of radicalisation in illegality in countries like Germany.</p>
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5.1.7 Economy

Migration in large numbers is one of the oldest soft threats perceived by host countries described in the academic literature. Economic consequences in countries of destination have long been perceived as an important threat to the extent that migrants are thought responsible for a decrease in the number of jobs for host citizens, the lower of the welfare state benefits or as a burden for public budgets due to the fact that migrants have to be rescued and governments have to pay different integration programs.

Table 10. Description of Economic in the reports

List of threats	Description of the threat in the reports
Economic	<p>Turks and Moroccans are the biggest migrant groups in the Netherlands and there are tensions between natives and migrants because of the perception that they draw a lot of the social benefits available.</p> <p>An uncontrolled number of migrants coming into the UK which is unsustainable.</p> <p>Locals fear that their society will be significantly affected by the immigrants who will claim part of their employment share and will also contribute to the increase in criminality rates and terrorist attacks.</p> <p>The integration of immigrants presents negative aspects such as the high weight of unemployment and low wages, the lack of access to post-compulsory education among second generations, etc.</p>

5.1.8 Civil unrest

Migration is also sometimes perceived as a reason for civil unrest. It is seen as a threat to the political stability as far as unhappy or disappointed migrants can use riots or manifestations to show their fury against the system.

Table 11. Description of Civil unrest in the reports

List of threats	Description of the threat in the reports
Civil unrest	<p>A lot of protests have taken place for this issue, as migrants were expecting other reception facilities and more humane living conditions.</p> <p>Difficulties in cultural and educational integration, increase of xenophobia and extreme nationalistic ideology,</p> <p>Attacks by transiting migrants against the public order to continue their way.</p> <p>Riots on the island (Lesbos). Fights between camp residents due to cultural differences</p> <p>Pro-migrant activists and anarchist groups that may attack borders with the participation of migrants</p>

5.1.9 Health problems/disease

Although it is included among threats to host countries, diseases are clearly a threat to both host countries and migrants themselves. The literature shows that among host countries' populations it is often believed that migrants can bring new diseases to Europe. Migrants can indeed suffer from different diseases due to different immune pasts or due to the conditions of journeys they take to arrive in Europe.

Table 12. Description of Health in the reports

List of threats	Description of the threat in the reports
Health (involves disease)	<p>Health problems among migrants, migration and communicable diseases;</p> <p>Food and waterborne diseases; vaccinations for refugees and migrants;</p> <p>Impact of sudden migration on people with non-communicable diseases; screening of refugees and migrants; breastfeeding in the context of large-scale migration.</p> <p>Health risks because of possible carriage of contagious diseases.</p>

5.1.10 Human smuggling and trafficking

Among the group of threats that affect migrants, host societies, as well as countries of origin and transit, are human smuggling and trafficking. An important number of reports relates to the trafficking of people as an increasing number of people contact crime organisations to find a way to pass through Europe.

Human smuggling and human trafficking are considered together in our classification despite the fact that they are different phenomena¹². The reason for that is that both imply organised crime and criminal networks and the relationships between these two "businesses" is increasing.

¹² Following UN definitions, human trafficking involves the recruitment, movement or harbouring of people for the purpose of exploitation - such as sexual exploitation, forced labour, slavery or organ removal and it can occur within a country or across borders. Human trafficking is therefore characterized by an act (recruitment, transportation, transfer, harbouring, or receipt of people), specific means (threats or use of force, deception,

Table 13. Description of Human smuggling and trafficking in the reports

List of threats	Description of the threat in the reports
Human smuggling and trafficking	<p>Human trafficking trends; Summary of human trafficking activities in 2018-2019.</p> <p>Illegal entry, illegal stay, human trafficking, use of fraudulent documents, misuse of asylum procedures.</p> <p>Currency counterfeiting, cybercrime, drug production/trafficking/distribution, environmental crime, fraud, intellectual property crime, people as a commodity (human trafficking), sports corruption, trafficking of firearms, links between SOC and terrorism.</p> <p>Conflicts in MENA as well as climate change contributing to displacement and increased numbers of refugees. Those places are facilitating the smuggling and trafficking of people.</p> <p>Smugglers were targeting ports with less stringent security checks to smuggle people into the UK.</p> <p>Alternative routes raise safety issues for migrants, due to light conditions during the night, lack of formal roads and missing knowledge of the terrain. They can also be used by migrant traffickers.</p> <p>Traffickers are taking advantage of the vulnerable condition of the unaccompanied minors and may exploit the opportunity to kidnap them and harvest their organs.</p> <p>Within the numbers of immigrants using Greece as a transit country, there is a significant percentage of unaccompanied minors. Some of them are orphans or trying to reach their close relatives in other central European countries. There is an opportunity of the organised criminal networks to kidnap them, harvest their organs and sell them to the increasingly demanding human organs black market.</p> <p>The smuggling of migrants brings a rise in the criminal activity and the number of criminal organizations issuing false documents for migrants and helping them in getting international protection in order to reach Western Europe, crossing borders illegally.</p> <p>Smugglers and recruiters transport migrants in Italy through unauthorized means, leading migrants to get into life-risks and debts.</p> <p>Illegal migration of the Kosovo citizens through Serbia and the smuggling of migrants through Serbia have exposed the lack of cooperation between the law enforcement institutions of both countries.</p> <p>Analytical view of the concept of human security in association with illegal migration.</p>

5.1.11 Corruption

Corruption also affects both referent objects, i.e. migrants and host countries. This threat can happen when state officials allow criminals to operate freely and turn a blind eye to their business of smuggling and trafficking people. In some cases, corruption can also imply asking for a bribe from migrants

fraud, abuse of power, or abusing someone's vulnerable condition) for the purpose of exploitation (for example sexual exploitation, forced labour, slavery or organ removal). On the other hand, human smuggling migrant smuggling is a crime that takes place only across borders. It consists in assisting migrants to enter or stay in a country illegally, for a financial or material gain. <https://www.unodc.org/e4j/en/secondary/human-trafficking-and-migrant-smuggling.html>

themselves. Thus, this threat is also related to border security, when border police or coastguards turn a blind eye when an illegal group of immigrants arrive brought by mafias.

Table 14. Description of Corruption in the reports

List of threats	Description of the threat in the reports
Corruption	Corruption by border policemen turning a blind eye to traffickers Many asylum-seekers complain that there are employees of the Asylum Service asking for money in order to handle a case earlier

5.1.12 Domestic violent extremism

Domestic violent extremism is sometimes difficult to differentiate from violent radicalisation and terrorism. In this case, domestic violent extremism does not imply the link of the individual with violent actions of terrorist organisations, but it can harm both migrants and host countries as citizens can become extremists over the issue of migration and right-wing parties' importance increase. This could mean xenophobic or exclusionary measures that negatively influence social cohesion.

Table 15. Description of Domestic violent extremism in the reports

List of threats	Description of the threat in the reports
Domestic violent extremism	<p>Clashes between local populations and African migrants.</p> <p>The murder of a local citizen by an African immigrant was the spark that ignited a violent clash between the local population and the African immigrant, 8 African immigrants were injured. The authorities decided to deport 700 African immigrants.</p> <p>The local population entered in a violent confrontation with the African immigrants in the city of Dely Ibrahim, the residents refused the presence of the immigrants in their neighbourhood due to the illegal activities practised by those immigrants (drug dealing, prostitution, alcohol selling and consumption).</p> <p>When migrants oppose home country regimes, they are seen as cultural threats; fear of the changing demography of EU countries from one ethnic group to a more multi-ethnic composition; Conflicts in MENA as well as climate change contributing to displacement and increased numbers of refugees.</p> <p>Reports of hate crimes against migrants coming from Germany, Hungary and Italy.</p> <p>Political framing of migration and asylum as a 'threat' influences public opinion in receiving societies.</p> <p>Greek nationalists' pork-and-booze BBQ targets Muslim refugees.</p> <p>Failure to maintain societal cohesion between the two largest migrant groups in the Netherlands (of Moroccan and Turkish origin) due to perceived incompatibility between welfare state and migration, and the cultural differences of these groups with Dutch values.</p> <p>Radicalization of migrants established in Bulgaria and entry of already radicalized people mixed with the migration flow. The awareness of this threat can cause rejection against migrants by Bulgarian population that might affect the perceptions migrants have of the country.</p> <p>1,500 extremists registered with law enforcement either currently are, or have at some point been employed in a socially significant service, while investigators</p>

	<p>claim shortcomings are present in the monitoring of radical sentiment among police officers, health workers, athletes and students.</p> <p>The economic recession accentuates the image of immigration as an economic threat, with the consequent increase in xenophobia. However, economic booms in themselves do not determine the acceptance of immigrants.</p>
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5.1.13 Environmental

The last of the issues/threats included in the classification is climate change and environmental deterioration. Environmental deterioration is a push factor causing people to migrate to other countries, but also a problem for host countries as, for example, refugee camps have proven to create a big amount of rubbish, both at sea and on land.

Table 16. Description of Environmental in the reports

List of threats	Description of the threat in the reports
Environmental	<p>Greece's refugee crisis creates a strain on an already fragile ecosystem</p> <p>Water pollution between Turkey and the Greek Islands, tons of debris left behind, no recycling of plastic containers used inside refugee camps</p>

5.1.14 Other threats

This point is miscellaneous of threats and issues included in the reports of the database. It includes threats to migrants and also to host countries. For example, this category includes different issues related to the culture and identity of host countries or tensions and accusations between countries for their management of the movement of people.

Table 17. Description of Other threats in the reports

List of threats	Description of the threat in the reports
Other threats	<p>Tension between Greece and Turkey leads to increased numbers of migrants from Turkey to Greece.</p> <p>Unaccompanied migrant children in Greece at Risk (insecurity, fear etc.)</p> <p>Women face daily dangers in Greek refugee camps.</p> <p>Potential abuse of the asylum system.</p> <p>When migrants oppose home country regimes, they are seen as cultural threats.</p> <p>Fear of the changing demography of EU countries from one ethnic group to a more multi-ethnic composition.</p> <p>Perceptions of migration being a threat to EU security and way of life.</p> <p>Migration is seen as a security threat to the identity and culture of the host country and affects the stability of host communities.</p> <p>The lack of solidarity on migrant sharing and others is threatening to undermine EU border security, with each member state having their own border security systems and policy in place.</p> <p>Advancements in technology could mean jobs that migrants fill could be automated. With no job, migrants could become reliant on the state for support which is something that the public dislike.</p>

	<p>The big number of unaccompanied minors that have arrived in Greece during the refugee crisis has pushed the governmental capabilities in their limits and in this way, there are many unaccompanied minors that are not living in special shaped areas</p> <p>Increasing number of unaccompanied children, dangers faced along routes</p> <p>Based on anecdotal evidence, modern communication technologies, especially social media, play a key role in encouraging migration.</p> <p>Turkish President threatened to reopen a route for migrants to reach Europe if no more support is received for a resettlement plan in Northern Syria.</p> <p>Decisions to migrate are rational choices under incomplete information based on the perception of costs and benefits.</p> <p>Perceptions are mentioned in relation to migrants perceiving Bulgaria as a transit country and perceiving their stay in detention centres and authorities' security measures as deterrence to their ongoing journey to Western Europe.</p> <p>Migrants making decisions based on the information they found and often they realise that the narratives of Italy and Europe as a welcoming place that they had become acquainted with are distant from reality.</p> <p>The Arab countries form a space for migration flows. The Arab Mashreq and Maghreb, for reasons connected to demographic transition and economic, social, and political conditions in the region, constitute an enormous reservoir of young workers highly inclined to emigrate.</p> <p>The European perceptions about “Illegal immigration” as a “mobile security threat”, pushed the European Union to launch several initiatives of different dimensions (covered mostly by security premonitions), oriented to the southern Mediterranean countries.</p>
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6 Classification and analysis of threats mentioned in the database

Once analysed the wording (discourse) of threats, classification and analysis of the threats themselves is made based on different variables that have been considered relevant to this research.

6.1 List of threats and referent objects threatened (migrants, host countries and threats to both)

Within the SLR in deliverable 2.2 and accordingly, the literature review carried out in the context of this deliverable (see above), we have found that migrants, sovereignty, the EU, integration, society, economy and political stability are identified as key areas perceived as threatened by migration.

After analysing the information received and classifying it according to the target population or referent object affected or perceived to be affected by the threat a table was compiled showing both the threats and the referent objects under threat. Table 18 shows the corresponding frequencies and percentages out of a total of 149 times that the various threats were mentioned in the documents or reports received¹³.

Table 18. Threats and referent objects threatened

Referent object	Threats	Frequencies	%	
Migrants	Death	7	4.7%	28.2%
	Detention and Deportation	17	11.4%	
	Discrimination	12	8.1%	
	Violence and Abuse	6	4%	
	Modern Slavery	0	0%	
Host countries	Violent Radicalisation and Terrorism	29	19.5%	43%
	Minor, Serious and Organised Crime	23	15.5%	
	Economic	7	4.7%	
	Civil Unrest	2	1.3%	
	Disease	3	2%	
Migrants and host countries	Human Smuggling and Trafficking	27	18.1%	28.8%
	Corruption	1	0.70%	
	Domestic Violent Extremism	13	8.70%	
	Environmental	2	1.30%	
TOTAL		149	100%	100%

The frequencies show how many times each threat was mentioned in the 138 documents. These threats are mentioned 149 times in the database. Since documents could mention more than one

¹³ These 149 mentions to threats plus the 28 other mentions of other threats not included in this classification, gives the total of 177 threats mentioned in the database.

threat, the total number of threats is higher than the number of documents. Violent radicalisation and terrorism (19.5%) stand out as the threat more times mentioned, followed by human smuggling and trafficking (18.1%) and detention and deportation (11.4%). Thus, one in each of the groups: migrants, host countries and both. Among the threats to migrants, discrimination reaches 8.1%. Among the threats or perceived threats to host countries, minor, serious and organised crime (15.5%) is also relevant. Among the threats affecting migrants and host countries, domestic violent extremism (8.7%) also shows up. The threat which did not appear in any of the reports is modern slavery. This may be due to its inclusion in human trafficking which includes forced labour and prostitution and which are considered forms of “modern slavery”. Corruption appeared as a less prevalent issue and mostly related to border security (i.e. border police, coastguards, can turn a blind eye when an illegal group of immigrants arrive brought by mafias).

If the information is analysed with respect to the referent object, threats related to host countries amounted for nearly half of the total percentage (43%)¹⁴. The total of threats affecting migrants account for 28.2% and the total percentage of threats that affect both migrants and host countries ascend to 28.8%.

6.2 Classification and analysis of the threats by actors who mention them (authors of the documents)

Splitting type of threats according to the author of the report or actor that identifies the threat, the resulting information (table 19) offers information about potential differences in the focus across actors.

Table 19. Threats and referent objects threatened

Threat	Academic/ Think Tank		Civil Society/ NGOs		Governmental/ Policymaking Body		Security/LEAs/ Border Security		Other institutions	
	Fr	%	Fr	%	Fr	%	Fr	%	Fr	%
Death	0	0.0%	2	10.5%	3	8.6%	0	0.0%	2	6.9%
Detention & deportation	2	5.3%	7	36.8%	7	20%	0	0%	1	3.4%
Discrimination	4	10.5%	3	15.9%	5	14.3%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%
Violence & abuse	0	0.0%	4	21.1%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	2	6.9%
Modern slavery	0	0.0%	0	0	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%
Violent radicalisation & terrorism	11	28.9%	2	10.5%	4	11.4%	6	21.4%	6	20.8%

¹⁴ Take into account that most of the reports stem from this type of countries.

Minor, serious & organised crime	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	2	5.7%	17	60.7%	4	13.8%
Economic	3	7.9%	1	5.2%	2	5.7%	0	0.0%	1	3.4%
Civil unrest	1	2.6%	0	0.0%	1	2.9%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%
Disease	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	3	8.6%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%
Human smuggling & trafficking	11	28.9%	0	0.0%	6	17.1%	5	17.9%	5	17.2%
Corruption	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	1	3.4%
Domestic violent extremism	5	13.2%	0	0.0%	2	5.7%	0	0.0%	6	20.8%
Environmental	1	2.6%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	1	3.4%
TOTAL	38	100%	19	100%	35	100%	28	100%	37	100%

Among threats mentioned by academic organisation and think tanks, violent radicalisation and terrorism stand out (28.9%) and human smuggling and trafficking (28.9%) (see figure 5). Their reports are clearly focused on these two threats.

Figure 5. Threats by academic's authors

From Civil Society organisations and NGOs' perspective, three threats appeared most frequently: detention and deportation (36.8%), violence and abuse (21.1%) and discrimination affecting migrants

(15.9%) (Figure 6). We can conclude that they are mainly focused on portraying the threats that affect migrants during their migration processes or once in the country of arrival.

Figure 6. Threats by civil societies

A comparative analysis of figures 5 and 6 show that there is a difference between academic/think tanks and NGO documents. Academics seem focused primarily on threats for host communities and host countries and migrants, while NGOs seem focused primarily on threats to migrants. Such differences are worth pointing out as this fact impacts where which type of narratives are transported – and this is something to take into account in policy and technical solutions.

The Governmental and policy-making bodies focus report similar threats than Civil Society and NGOs, they primarily point to detention and deportation problems (20%) and secondly to discrimination (14.3%) (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Threats by policymaking bodies

The main threats stated in the reports of Security Practitioners, Law enforcement agencies and Border Agencies (figure 8) in the report produced by them since 2015 are those issues linked to minor, serious and organised crime. This category is followed by violent radicalisation and terrorism (21.4%) and human trafficking and smuggling (17.9%) in the concerns shown in the reports.

The comparison of figure 8 with previous figures of threats mentioned by different organisations indicates that the range of threats reported by LEAs/security and border agencies is quite small. These reports identified only three of the twelve threats. After minor, serious and organised crime and violent radicalisation and terrorism, LEA/security reports are focused on human trafficking and smuggling. Thus, it can be said that they focus their analysis of threats and perceptions of threats, more than 80%, in the host countries.

Figure 8. Threats by security practitioners

The reports from 'others' (other types of organisations) were mostly focused on violent radicalisation and terrorism and domestic violent extremism (both 20.8%), followed by threats of human smuggling and trafficking (17.2%) (Figure 9).¹⁵

Figure 9. Threats by 'others'

¹⁵ The overall number of "others" is quite small, so we cannot be completely sure about the results.

6.3 Classification and analysis of the threats by level of the organization

In the next step, we carried out an analysis of the documents and subsequent classification of threats based on the level of the organization that has produced the document. Table 20 provides an overview of threats and the level of organisations that focus their attention on them. As this overview shows, reports from international organisation focus strongly on detention and deportation (24.3%) while European organisations do it in minor, serious and organised crime. National organisation emphasizes issues related to violent radicalisation (29.2%) and regional/local organisations are focused on human smuggling and trafficking (40%).

Table 20. Number of times the threats have been mentioned by level of the organization

Referent object	Threat	Author									
		International		European		National		Regional		Other	
		Fr	%	Fr	%	Fr	%	Fr	%	Fr	%
Migrants	Death	4	8.9%	1	3.2%	1	1.6%	1	20.0%	0	0.0%
	Detention & deportation	11	24.4%	1	3.2%	4	6.2%	0	0.0%	1	33.3%
	Discrimination	6	13.3%	3	9.7%	3	4.6%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%
	Violence & abuse	3	6.7%	0	0.0%	2	3.0%	1	20.0%	0	0.0%
	Modern slavery	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%
Host countries	Violent radicalisation & terrorism	3	6.7%	5	16.1%	19	29.2%	0	0.0%	2	66.7%
	Minor, serious & organised crime	2	4.4%	9	29.0%	12	18.5%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%
	Economic	2	4.4%	2	6.4%	3	4.6%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%
	Civil unrest	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	2	3.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%
Migrants and host countries	Disease	1	2.2%	0	0.0%	2	3.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%
	Human smuggling & trafficking	7	15.6%	7	22.7%	11	17.0%	2	40.0%	0	0.0%
	Corruption	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	1	1.6%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%
	Domestic violent extremism	4	8.9%	3	9.7%	5	7.7%	1	20.0%	0	0.0%
	Environment	2	4.4%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%
TOTAL		45	100%	31	100%	65	100%	5	100%	3	100%

As we can be seen in figure 10 below, the organisations on an international level address a wide range of threats, with a special focus on detention and deportation. It is clear that these documents also pay attention to human smuggling and trafficking. Internationally focused reports thus seem devoted to analysing all possible threats that affect migrants, host societies and both.

Figure 10. Threats by international level

As illustrated in figure 11, organisations at the European level seem to pay greatest attention to minor, serious and organised crime or at least mention the most in the reports collected. They also treat issues of human trafficking and smuggling and to threats of violent radicalisation and terrorism. This suggests that these threats raise concerns at the level of European institutions and organisations.

Figure 11. Threats by European level

Organisations at the national level (Figure 12), which constitute the most abundant group of documents in our sample, we found that the most frequently mentioned threats are those linked to

violent radicalisation and terrorism (29.2%) followed by minor, serious and organised crime (18.5%). Human smuggling and trafficking are further relevant threats identified by organisations that work at the national level. This indicates that the activities related these threats are the ones that most concern the different organizations and institutions at the national level of the countries analysed in this research project.

Figure 12. Threats by National level

As for organisations at the regional and other levels, which are the least abundant within our dataset, the former reported mostly on human smuggling and trafficking (figure 13), while documents from the latter groups reported primarily about violent radicalisation and terrorism.

Figure 13. Threats by regional level

6.4 Classification and analysis of the threats by countries affected

The following (figure 14) is a classification of the migration-related threats identified according to the country/countries affected by these issues.

Figure 14. Number of times the threats have been mentioned by country affected

Greece emerged as the country with the highest number of migration-related threats, or the country portrayed as affected by more, likely due to its geographical position close to Turkey, the route through the Balkans and the diversity of migrants it receives from various countries. The number of threats that affected or affect to Greece may also be related to the fact that international and European organisations reports incorporated analyses of the situation in Greece during the recent arrival of refugees/migrants from Syria. Germany was also in the focus of the European asylum system during 2015 and 2016. Figure 14 also shows that Belgium is a country affected by most of the issues reported in the database, perhaps this may be connected to the issues of violent radicalization and terrorist attacks suffered on your soil.

Figure 15 groups threats by the geographical area of occurrence. According to reports, most of the migration-related threats are located in continental Europe (82%). In addition, the MENA region, the acronym for the Middle East and Northern Africa countries, is a further focus in reports (12%). The Mediterranean Sea is referred to as a transit route for migrants. Hence, mention of the MENA region does not mean that the threat comes from a specific country in this area. Moreover, European continental and MENA countries border with the Mediterranean Sea.¹⁶ Only one report references threats from a worldwide point of view what seems quite reasonable as PERCEPTIONS project focuses on perceptions of Europe.

¹⁶ In this group, Mediterranean Sea, we have only included those threats that did not mention continental Europe or MENA region in particular.

Figure 15. Threats mentioned in reports according to places in the world where they take place

6.5 Classification and analysis of the threats by type of country

In this section, the disparate threats identified are differentiated according to the type of country (origin, transit and destination). This analysis allows us to better understand whether there are disparities in the relevance or attention paid to specific threats by countries depending on their status as origin, transit or destination. Findings reported in Table 21 show that countries of origin and transit share a focus on threats that affect migrants and host countries: human smuggling and trafficking (25% in each group); countries of origin also mentioned the issue of domestic violent extremism in host countries (25%) that affect migrants and locals. Destination countries, which are the biggest group in the database, are focused on host country threats, paying special attention to issues related to violent radicalisation and terrorism (21.3%).

Table 21. Threats by types of countries

Referent object	Threat	Type of country					
		Origin		Transit		Destination	
		Fr	%	Fr	%	Fr	%
Migrants	Death	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	7	6.0%
	Detention & deportation	3	19.0%	2	12.5%	12	10.3%
	Discrimination	0	0.0%	3	18.9%	9	7.8%
	Violence and abuse	1	6.0%	2	12.5%	3	2.6%
	Modern slavery	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%

Host countries	Violent radicalisation and terrorism	2	12.5%	2	12.5%	25	21.3%
	Minor, serious and organised crime	2	12.5%	0	0.0%	21	18.0%
	Economic	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	7	6.0%
	Civil unrest	0	0.0%	1	6.2%	1	0.8%
Migrants and host countries	Disease	0	0.0%	1	6.2%	2	1.7%
	Human smuggling & trafficking	4	25.0%	4	25.0%	19	16.2%
	Corruption	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	1	0.8%
	Domestic violent extremism	4	25.0%	1	6.2%	8	6.8%
	Environmental	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	2	1.7%
TOTAL		16	100%	16	100.0%	117	100.0%

Figure 16 provides more detail on origin countries. It suggests that reports about origin countries emphasise issues of human trafficking and domestic violent extremism followed detention and deportation. This makes sense as it suggests a picture of migrants worried about their future in their destination countries but also in the migration process itself.

Figure 16. Threats by origin countries

Reports about transit countries focused on a wider range of threats (Figure 17), mostly human smuggling and trafficking followed by discrimination.

Figure 17. Threats by transit countries

Documents about host or destination countries reported most of the total number of threats. These documents also mentioned human smuggling and trafficking but focused even more strongly on violent radicalisation and terrorism and in minor, serious and organised crime.

Figure 18. Threats by destination countries

6.6 Classification and analysis of the threats by year of the document/report

Figure 19. Frequencies of threats by year of the document

We also compared reported threats according to the publication date of the documents in order to see whether the documents from different years focused on similar issues. Figure 19 shows that reports in 2015 have a peak for mentions of minor, serious and organised crime. In 2016, the line on the figure is quite flat so they don't focus on a particular threat. In 2017, there is a peak in human smuggling and trafficking followed very close by minor, serious and organised crime. The 2018 line reaches a top in violent radicalisation and terrorism threat though human smuggling and trafficking are also remarkable. Documents from 2019 deal mainly with detention and deportation issues, but also with violent radicalisation and terrorism and human smuggling and trafficking.

6.7 List of threats by areas of security-related policy (Violent radicalisation and terrorism, Minor, serious and organised crime, Human smuggling and trafficking and Border security)

To better understand the migration-related threats most frequently mentioned across documents, a classification of documents according to security policy areas was created (following PERCEPTIONS deliverable 2.3). Initially, the classification was meant to focus on violent radicalisation and terrorism, human smuggling and trafficking as well as border security. We added to the D2.3 the classification "Minor, serious and organised crime" threat as it can be considered as one of the main threats affecting national/internal security.

Previously in this deliverable, we provided descriptions of current threats. Below, a description of border security threats is presented, as PERCEPTIONS project is also concerned with linkages of threats and threat perceptions with security-related policies. As can be seen in the descriptions in table 22, reports about border security tend to deal with problems in borders related to identification, detention or stay in accommodation centres mainly and with other issues such as corruption and abuse of power by border police, illegal detentions and returns, problems related to border policies or misuse of the asylum system. In this context, special attention is paid to women but mainly to unaccompanied minors. Border security is also affected by human smuggling and trafficking as far as those criminal

organisations try to overcome such controls, try to take advantage of security problems and put migrants' lives at risk. Sometimes, the reports also mention problems and tensions between bordering countries related to the patrol or the lack of it.

Table 22. Description of Border security in the reports

Threat	Description of the threat in the reports
Border security	<p>Inadequate shelter conditions; overcrowded reception centres in Cyprus and Greece; inadequate staying conditions at reception centres; deaths and sexual violence, violence, abuse, exploitation and severe psychological distress, smuggling trafficking at the reception centres or through their journey to the transit and destination country disappearances along land routes and sea journeys to Greece.</p> <p>Refugee flows through Greece's land borders have started rising again, causing frustration among EU and Greek authorities.</p> <p>Hundreds of unaccompanied children on the Greek island of Lesbos are exposed to inhuman and degrading living conditions.</p> <p>Dire Living Conditions for Asylum Seekers on the Islands, irregular entry at the land border of Greece and Turkey.</p> <p>The dangers and insecurity (unaccompanied) migrant children face in the destination countries (e.g. physical and verbal abuse, overcrowded reception centres, substandard sanitary conditions, fire hazards, etc.</p> <p>A strategic report on the use of cash by criminal groups as a facilitator for money laundering.</p> <p>Number of deaths recorded along land routes at Europe's borders.</p> <p>Illegal entry, illegal stay, human trafficking, use of fraudulent documents, misuse of asylum procedures, inability to execute returns, stress on border infrastructures.</p> <p>Stronger anti-immigration laws to reduce non-British migrants coming into the UK.</p> <p>Conservatives want to introduce stronger border controls post-Brexit to make it harder for serious criminals to come to the UK.</p> <p>The lack of solidarity on migrant sharing and others is threatening to undermine EU border security, with each member state having their own border security systems and policy in place.</p> <p>Frontex recorded that 57,034 crossing attempts were made in 2018 compared to 23,063 in 2017.</p> <p>Military involvement in controlling migration flows into Europe through activities in the Mediterranean Sea and the Sahel in Africa.</p> <p>Tougher immigration checks in France was pushing organised criminals towards ports like Zeebrugge as a new route for people smugglers.</p> <p>Migration and border control measures to counter-terrorism.</p> <p>Increase in mixed immigrant influx reaching Greek small islands which lack the necessary (hosting) premises.</p> <p>Spreading of fake news and taking advantage of the need of refugees/immigrants to travel from the transit country to their destination country.</p>

	<p>Alternative routes raise safety issues for migrants, due to light conditions during the night, lack of formal roads and missing knowledge of the terrain. They can also be used by migrant traffickers.</p> <p>Turkish President threatened to reopen a route for migrants to reach Europe if no more support is received for a resettlement plan in Northern Syria.</p> <p>Infiltration of terrorists among the migration flow, difficulties in cultural and educational integration.</p> <p>Poverty, war and political instability in the countries of origin, closing of borders and denial of travelling documents to third-country nationals, long distances they need to travel to get to the EU, difficulties to find residence and work due to regulation and social perceptions.</p> <p>Bulgaria has normalised mass detention of migrants and refugees, while it has built a razor-wire fence on its South-Eastern border and regularly undertakes pushbacks at its border with Turkey.</p> <p>Summary detentions, pushbacks and abuses at the border, lack of basic services, climate of xenophobia and intolerance.</p> <p>The sharp surge in the number of Kosovo migrants to the EU during 2014-2015 is considered to have occurred as a result of criminal networks of smugglers operating in Kosovo and Serbia, which were smuggling migrants to bring them to the EU via illegal Serbian routes.</p> <p>Perception of Lower Border Controls: "the perception that leaving was easier due to low border controls was both a driver and trigger for Tunisians who left in the aftermath of the revolution".</p>
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Table 23 illustrates that if we consider the four major areas of policy in the context of law enforcement actions, a total of 115 threats of the 177 mentioned in the database can be classified as direct threats to the security of host countries. Nearly 25.2% consider the threat of violent radicalisation and terrorism followed by 23.5% that consider human smuggling and trafficking. Minor, serious and organised crime represents 20% of these 115 threats. 31.3% of the issues are linked to border security. Border issues and migration have been the centre of the development of the European migration agenda at different relevant moments of the European integration process and most of the threats included have an impact or are related to the borders of Europe.

Table 23. Classification of database information by security-related areas of policies

Security-related areas	Frequencies of threats	%
Violent radicalisation and terrorism	29	25.2%
Minor, serious and organised crime	23	20.0%
Human smuggling and trafficking	27	23.5%
Border security	36	31.3%
TOTAL	115	100%

6.8 Classification and analysis of the documents by time of the threat

A final classification of the documents has been made based on the year in which the threat appeared or is perceived, rather than the year in which the document was published. The threats have been classified according to time periods and with respect to the specific year(s) of the occurrence of the threats.

When classifying the reports according to the date during which the threats took place, it has been decided to cluster them into three different periods. The key milestone for differentiating the three periods was set in the year 2015, which marks the beginning of the so-called “refugee crisis”. Therefore, three main categories were used to identify threats by date: threats that arose before 2015, those that were reported for the time between 2015 and 2018, as the years of greatest arrival of migrants and refugees to Europe, and those reported more recently, after 2018. Figure 20 shows that threats or issues are mainly dated between 2015 and 2018. After this year, the amount of threats perceived goes down very sharply.

Figure 20. Documents by time of the threat

It should be noted that 8 documents did not provide clear information about the beginning of the threat. These have been labelled as ‘undetermined’ (see figure 20).

6.9 Other threats encountered

After analysing the information received and following the initial classification of threats used for this analysis, 110 documents were found that did not report new threats compared to 28 documents which mentioned new threats¹⁷. Although we have called them ‘new threats’¹⁸, in reality, some of them are new or specific manifestations of old threats.

The new threats identified in the documents are:

- **Abuse of the asylum system:** In different documents, the fear of possible abuse of the asylum system is mentioned, since some people without eligible reasons to have refugee status may request for asylum to obtain certain advantages or to stay longer in the country.

¹⁷ As some documents more than on

¹⁸ ‘New threats’ or at least different from those pointed out in the SLR of deliverable 2.2.

- **Cultural threats and national identity:** Some reports outlined that immigration can challenge the culture of host countries and accepted European continental tradition more broadly as well as 'the way of life' and thus 'endanger' national identity by making societies more multicultural and multi-ethnic. They further highlighted the problem of 'non-integration' by immigrants.
- **Unaccompanied minors and overcrowding in refugee camps:** This challenge is mainly found in documents about Greece, as they highlight the challenges of arrivals by unaccompanied minors, their assimilation and integration in the country, together with the fact that refugee camps cannot absorb an unlimited number of immigrant populations, as this could be even more dangerous for those children who travel alone. Due to the overpopulation of refugee camps, children often lack a special place for them and in consequence suffer abuses such as sexual harassment, discrimination, etc.
- **Women:** Women are hardly mentioned in the reports. Where they appear, women, together with children, are described as a vulnerable target for human smuggling and trafficking and sexual violence.
- **Diplomatic problems:** Several reports address the concern of a conflict with Turkey because this country receives and maintains a huge number of immigrants and Turkey has threatened Europe more than once with an opening of its borders.

7 Threats related to ICT, social and digital media

Documents provided by partners also considered the importance of technology (understood here in a broad sense, e.g. social networks, instant messaging applications, search engines, etc.). Overall, 129 documents did not mention technology, while 9 documents did refer to the importance of technology in relation to some of the threats and security issues stated. Those 9 documents report 12 threats (figure 21). ICTs are related to violent radicalisation and terrorism (50%) and also to human smuggling and trafficking (25%), discrimination (12.5%) and minor and serious crime (12.5%), and they also refer to two new threats identified above: minors and cultural threats. Here we present the analysis of those documents.

Figure 21. The importance of technology is mentioned by threats

Technology, in terms of its relationship with migratory movements, can have a positive influence, facilitating or diminishing the need for displacement, but it can also have a negative impact that drives to worsen the conditions of these processes, and consequently the problems or threats that seem to be related to them. On the positive side, ICTs are reported to favour and facilitate migration processes in some ways: better knowledge of the place of destination, route, links with people who migrated before or ICTs and mobile phones can be used by migrants sharing information about the best migration routes to follow and “modern communications technology can also be used for messaging which informs about the risks associated with migration as long as it is presented in attractive and convincing form”¹⁹, diminishing part of the threat that migrants face such as death or violence and abuse.

ICTs can be a tool to better integration decreasing the problems and or threats faced in the host countries, such as discrimination. In this sense, the Spanish Ministry of Foreign Affairs, European Union and Cooperation declared at the III African Plan that the digital age opens up infinite possibilities for communication and the creation of public opinion as well as to generate contact networks, but also the need to attend to new sources of power and global competitiveness. The already known as digital diplomacy opens a very powerful public sphere, without barriers, where ideas, values and opinion are

¹⁹ <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/bitstream/JRC111774/kjnd29060enn.pdf>; P.17

created collaboratively. This digital dimension goes hand in hand with the rest of the communication initiatives and this can improve the activism of digital communication platforms and use more traditional media such as television and radio to bring the African reality closer to Spain and the Spanish reality to Africa, using it as a soft power tool.²⁰

Another report highlights that references to distress or fear concerning migratory journeys or the initial arrival are rarely displayed on Facebook, though successful journeys or arrivals were often announced with religious messages of gratitude. These posts receive a high number of “likes” and congratulatory messages, mainly from other co-nationals who appear to live abroad and in the migrants’ countries of origin. ICTs could help increase migration as it makes travel easier and safer, but they can also influence the decline of these processes insofar as “technology enables more people to work abroad without migrating.”²¹ Moreover, “investment in technology and new possibilities for remote work could decrease demand for longer-term migration of high- and medium-skilled workers”²².

This panorama could alleviate the threats perceived in host countries such as particularly those related to criminal activities, the arrival of terrorism taking advantage of migratory movements, or economic consequences for native workers as well as civil unrest or diseases. But it could also lessen the burden, problems and threats to migrant themselves (death, detention and deportation, discrimination or violence and abuse) and those that affect migrants and host countries (human smuggling and trafficking, corruption, domestic violent extremism or environment problems). Or decrease the problems at borders to the extent that “the application of advanced technology that provides enhanced control and enforcement of external borders in order to protect freedom of movement internally”.²³

However, ICTs are also related to a negative impact that drives to worsen the conditions of these processes, and consequently the problems or threats that seem to be related to them. There is a group of ‘hybrid threats’ associated with migration, particularly the weaponization of migrants, human smuggling and trafficking, and terrorist infiltration”²⁴. Another report presents information based on interviews conducted in Eritrea, Ethiopia, Somalia and in diaspora communities to assure that “anecdotal evidence suggests modern communications technology, especially social media, plays a key role in encouraging migration. Those who have already arrived in host countries often exaggerate their ‘successes’ when posting on social media, leading populations at home to believe their lives will dramatically improve if they migrate. Mobile phones and social media platforms are used by traffickers to demand payments and make threats...”²⁵ Another report assures that for almost all types of organised crime, criminals are deploying and adapting technology with increasing skill and ever greater

²⁰http://www.exteriores.gob.es/Portal/es/SalaDePrensa/Multimedia/Publicaciones/Documents/2019_PLAN%20AFRICA.pdf

²¹ <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/bitstream/JRC111774/kjnd29060enn.pdf>; p.29.

²² <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/bitstream/JRC111774/kjnd29060enn.pdf>, p. 43.

²³ <https://www.dahrendorf-forum.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/03/Militarising-Migration-Julia-Himmrich.pdf>, p.2

²⁴ <https://www.dahrendorf-forum.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/03/Militarising-Migration-Julia-Himmrich.pdf>, p. 1

²⁵ <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/bitstream/JRC111774/kjnd29060enn.pdf>; P.17

effect. This is now, perhaps, the greatest challenge facing law enforcement authorities around the world, including in the EU.²⁶

“Criminal actors in the EU display a high degree of adaptability and creativity in exploiting and employing new technologies. While not all criminal activities are driven by technological developments, the internet and ever-increasing connectivity have an impact on virtually all types of serious and organised crime. Innovation in technology and logistics increasingly enable OCGs (Organised Crime Groups) to commit crime anonymously, anywhere and anytime without being physically present”²⁷. Some reports provide information about how ICTs are used by OCGs in their activities related to migration. Many OCGs have expanded their crime portfolio in response to the sustained high level of demand for smuggling services since 2015²⁸, and they operate in a context of “A growing number of online platforms and applications offer new ways of transferring money and are not always regulated to the same degree as traditional financial service providers”.²⁹ In this context, technology is also used to forge documents by smugglers and traffickers.

Unfortunately, there are many mafias and networks that take advantage of the situation of people and nowadays migrant smuggling is a multi-national business in which we can find migrant smugglers originating from over 122 countries are involved in facilitating the journeys of irregular migrants to the EU. Most migrant smuggling networks are composed of various nationalities involving both EU and non-EU nationals. Migrant smuggling networks heavily rely on social media to advertise smuggling services, they make use of ride-sharing applications and P2P accommodation platforms to provide a cover for their smuggling activities, this leaves regular users at the risk of inadvertently becoming facilitators by unknowingly transporting or hosting irregular migrants. Service packages offered by migrant smugglers now frequently include the provision of fraudulent travel and identity documents the fraudulent documents allow irregular migrants to enter and move within the EU as well as to change from irregular to legalised residence status under false pretences or by using fake identities. Document fraud has emerged as a key criminal activity linked to the migration crisis this means the provision of fraudulent documents will continue to represent a substantial threat to EU security.³⁰

All these criminal activities are also linked to terrorist organisations. Schmid (2016) describes an example in which a smuggler advertised on his social media page the costs of the sea journey from Libya to Italy as US \$ 1,000 per adult. For a package involving also a flight from Turkey to Libya, it amounted US \$ 3,700, with children costing US \$ 500.90. Assuming that the smugglers of people in Libya had to share their profit with terrorists on the coast of Libya from where many boats depart and assuming that one third has to be paid to the terrorists, that would have left the terrorist organisation with more than US \$ 100 million in 2015 alone (a conservative estimate). That kind of money goes a long way to recruit new members for IS and pay for arms, explosives, false travel documents, safe houses, bribes and whatever else is needed to finance terrorism.³¹ Terrorist organisations, such as

²⁶ https://www.europol.europa.eu/sites/default/files/documents/report_socta2017_1.pdf

²⁷ https://www.europol.europa.eu/sites/default/files/documents/report_socta2017_1.pdf

²⁸ https://www.europol.europa.eu/sites/default/files/documents/report_socta2017_1.pdf,

²⁹ https://www.europol.europa.eu/sites/default/files/documents/report_socta2017_1.pdf P. 16

³⁰ https://www.europol.europa.eu/sites/default/files/documents/report_socta2017_1.pdf P.

³¹ <https://www.icct.nl/wp-content/uploads/2016/05/Alex-P.-Schmid-Links-between-Terrorism-and-Migration-1.pdf>

DAESH, have used social media to engage new followers showing videos of desperate refugees drowning while portraying life under the Caliphate as harmonious and orderly (Schmid, 2016).

This brings us to an important part of the negative effects of ICTs that is how new technologies can open doors to terrorism much more easily and quickly. Figure 21 presents where the technology is mentioned in relation to specific threats in order to see in a more visual way in which threats are more often linked to technology.

As we can see (figure 21 above), the importance of technology is especially related to the threat of violent radicalisation and terrorism followed closely by the threat of minor, serious and organised crime. This link may illustrate how extremist movements such as the Salafist movement made a successful entry into the 21st century due to the opportunities offered by the Internet as an efficient means of ideological dissemination. This is how an untold number of forums, websites, social media accounts and online video channels related to Salafism flourished on the web in order to radicalise and recruit new members. Both IS and AQ continue to seek out new online vectors for their propaganda.³² The attempted shift to open-source and in some cases de-centralised, distributed platforms relying on blockchain or peer-to-peer technology testify to the fact that terrorist organisations continue to lay claim to a degree of technological adaptability and are often early adopters of new technologies. Their efforts stand as a testimony to jihadist groups' continuous willingness to respond and adapt to shifting dynamics and developments.³³

Some debates about UK national security have also focussed on managing the threat posed by British Islamist fighters returning from Syria and Iraq. At the same time, foreign national perpetrators of terrorist attacks will not necessarily be accurately classified in data as 'migrants', they may be in the country as tourists or visitors of some other type. This complicates attempts to clearly show a relationship between migration and terrorism.³⁴

³² <https://www.europol.europa.eu/publications-documents/online-jihadist-propaganda-%E2%80%93-2018-in-review>

³³ <https://www.europol.europa.eu/publications-documents/online-jihadist-propaganda-%E2%80%93-2018-in-review>

³⁴ <https://migrationobservatory.ox.ac.uk/resources/commentaries/migration-and-security-navigating-the-risks/>

8 Conclusions

This deliverable stems from the analysis of information provided by consortium partners about migration-related threats. Prior to the analysis of this data, a review of the state-of-the-art of research on the perceived migration-related threats was conducted. The information was presented around three main research questions:

- What are the main issues that are perceived as affecting security/ border security related to migration processes and how they are mentioned in the reports of different organisations?
- What are the characteristics of the documents from security practitioners, policymakers and civil society organisations?
- What are the characteristics of the threats identified and collected from those reports?

Threats that affect directly the security of host societies are the most frequently mentioned issues across reports. Particularly relevant is the issue of violent radicalisation and terrorism. Among the threats perceived as affecting both migrants and host, countries are human smuggling and trafficking, and among those that affect migrants, detention and deportation. Border security stands out among the security-related areas of policies analysed.

As highlighted before, this research classifies, among other items, the reports according to countries determined as countries of origin, transit and destination. The documents of this research come especially from the host countries due to the number of countries that participated and the large number of reports we received from them. This means that the conclusions we have reached are, in part, broadly the vision of the destination countries. This conclusion points to the need of the PERCEPTIONS project to assess the perspectives and narratives of countries which migrants transit through as well as of their countries of origin. In this sense, this report is also the view of the institutional actors (think tanks, policymakers, NGOs and security practitioners) that needs and will be complemented with the perspective of migrants, their perceptions and narratives, and other practitioners from different sectors, in PERCEPTIONS project.

Documents from academic organisations and think tanks are predominant in the database followed by others, such as media, newspapers, and governmental and policymaking bodies. The nature of these documents, in term of the level of the organisation that wrote or publish them, is mainly national. Hence, international and comparative research as PERCEPTIONS project will be welcome. Moreover, most of the documents date from 2018 and 2019 while they portray threats related to 2015 and 2016, thus updated research is also needed.

The qualitative analysis, and its comparison with the literature reviewed at the beginning of this deliverable and in deliverable 2.2 of PERCEPTIONS project, show that no special new phrasing of threats is done, despite the fact that some of the threats are being framed in a new way such as violent radicalisation or human trafficking and different threats are mentioned in reports, particularly the situation of unaccompanied minors. The qualitative research shows how each group of people perceive each other's role in the problem and issues. Sometimes narratives about different threats are linked to others: for example, cases of deportations of imams due to their indoctrination of young people or disease and environmental problems due to rubbish in overcrowded detention/accommodation centres.

In relation to threats identified through the reports, an important finding is that the threat of violent radicalisation and terrorism seems prominent in most of the reports of host countries; this means an imaginary that links this threat with those who come from outside. Notably, host countries appeared more worried about the consequences that might come with the arrival of migrants than the threats migrants may suffer in their journeys to arrive in Europe. Some of the “expected” threats, based on the SLR presented in D2.2 and the academic review carried out in the first part of this research, barely appear in the documents collected, such as corruption and modern slavery. Another remarkable finding is the salience of border security. The documents consider issues at borders, such as detention and deportation or human smuggling and trafficking, control over their borders and disputes in the presence of large flows of immigrants. Borders are mentioned as deserving special attention regarding the possible entry of criminals/terrorists who can cross under the chaos of such large numbers of people.

The countries Algeria, Egypt and Tunisia were classified in this deliverable as origin countries, but the fact is that these countries are also transit countries. This is because many migrants from Sub-Saharan countries travel to these countries and stay there for a while until they have the opportunity to try to reach Europe. These three countries thus act as transit and origin countries and have the same worries about threats, namely threats of human smuggling and trafficking.

Among the actors who identify the threats, the ones who have included the broadest view of aspects or issues related to security are academic and think-tanks reports, while documents by security practitioners are much narrower in focus. Civil society reports analyse issues such as human trafficking and emphasise that the children and women are particularly vulnerable migration groups.

An additional analysis on the impact of new technologies on migration, perceptions and threats is included in this report. However, there are very few reports that are focused on and mainly related to technologies and its relationship with migration along with diverse threats. New technologies are today, a very powerful weapon for organized crimes and illegal trafficking of immigrants. This means that Europe needs to create new methods to prevent and fight the challenges that arise from these threats. PERCEPTIONS project is a great opportunity to observe and analyse the importance of these and their impact on these issues.

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Annex I. Template for data collection

T2.4 Threats and Security Issues												
Name of the Organization/Institution/Entity who wrote the report	Level of the Organisation	Type of the Organization/Institution/Entity who wrote the report	Threat/security issue identified	Detailed description of the threat/security issue	Populations which will be affected by the threat/issue	Detailed description of the cause of the issue/threat (perceptions/false narratives)	Time of Incident/Threat (Year, Month)	Place of Incident/Threat	Title of the report	Year of the report	weblink to the report/document etc.	Comments

Annex II. Threats by countries that identify them.

Example: Spain

Threats	
Death	
Detention and Deportation	Yes
Discrimination	Yes
Violence and Abuse	
Modern Slavery	
Violent Radicalisation and Terrorism	
Minor, Serious and Organised Crime	
Economic	Yes
Civil Unrest	Yes
Disease	
Human Smuggling and Trafficking	Yes
Corruption	
Domestic Violent Extremism	
Environmental	